

Total free amino acid content and some probable amino acids present in Njavara as compared with PTB20 grain.

Condition	Duration (d)	Amino acids identified	Total free amino acid content (mg g ⁻¹)
<i>Black-glumed Njavara</i>			
Wetland	99	DL-2-amino-N-butyric acid and DL-isoleucine	0.316
Open upland	94	L-histidine monohydrochloride, L-leucine, DL-methionine and L-proline	0.670
50-70% shaded upland	93	DL-2-amino-N-butyric acid, L-cysteine hydrochloride monohydrate, DL-methionine and DL-isoleucine	0.814
20-40% shaded upland	93	DL-threonine, DL-methionine and L-leucine	0.334
<i>Golden yellow-glumed Njavara</i>			
Wetland	103	L-histidine monochloride, L-ornithine monohydrochloride and DL-isoleucine	0.089
Open upland	95	DL-2-amino-N-butyric acid, L-proline, DL-methionine and L-leucine	0.424
50-70% shaded upland	102	DL-threonine, DL-methionine and DL-isoleucine	0.169
20-40% shaded upland	99	DL-threonine, DL-methionine and L-leucine	0.164
PTB20 in wetland situation	120	DL-serine	0.183

Seven promising breeding lines of the F₈ generation were studied for stability to pest resistance and agronomic characters during the 1993-95 monsoon seasons. In the field, 30-d-old seedlings of these test lines were transplanted at 10- × 20- cm spacing in two 2-m rows along with checks TN1 (susceptible) and Ptb33 (resistant). At maximum tillering stage, all plants were inoculated with Xoo by clip inoculation method. Recommended agronomic practices were followed to raise the crop. Observations were recorded for all hills 50 d after transplanting when gall midge incidence peaked. Likewise BLB-inoculated plants were observed for disease symptoms at maximum disease pressure.

At harvest, grain was collected for re-sowing the next wet season. Grain and plant characters were also recorded. In the glasshouse, these lines were screened against *N. lugens*; feeding and probing mark studies were also carried out.

Except for pureline IET6286, all seven breeding lines were derived from a widely cultivated variety Ruchi, which is resistant to gall midge and moderately resistant to BLB (Table 1). IR64 is resistant to the Raipur BPH insect population. RM1 (Raipur mutant), also used as a donor, is resistant to BLB but susceptible to gall midge. IR19661-23-3-2 and IR27325-111-2-1 are gall midge-susceptible but

Pest resistance

New rice breeding lines with multiple pest resistance

D. J. Pophaly A. Gupta, and G. R. Sahu, Entomology Department, Indira Gandhi Krishi Vishwavidyalaya, Raipur 492012, India

Brown planthopper (BPH) (*Nilaparvata lugens*), gall midge (*Orseolia oryzae*), and

bacterial leaf blight (BLB) disease (*Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* [Xoo]) are widespread in the Chhattisgarh region of Madhya Pradesh. To overcome this major constraint to selecting proper varieties in the integrated pest management program, we sought to develop new breeding lines with multiple pest resistance.

Table 1. Agronomic characters of advanced breeding lines.

Breeding line	Parentage	Test weight (g) 1,000 seed	Duration (d)	Hull color	Kernel color	Grain dimension ^a	Plant type ^b	Plant color
R712-1-65-1-1	Ruchi/IR19661-23-3-2	33	125	Light golden	White	LS	SD	Green
R710-3-37-1-1-1	Ruchi/IR27325-111-2-1	31	125	Light golden	White	LS	SD	Green
IET6286	-	23	155	Deep golden	White	LS	T	Green
R746-2-34-1-2-1	IR64/Ruchi	24	125	Straw	White	LS	SD	Green
R714-2-9-3-2-2	RMI/Ruchi	28	125	Straw	White	LS	SD	Purple
R714-1-19-1-5-1	RMI/Ruchi	27	125	Straw	White	LS	SD	Purple
R720-1-91-2-1-1	Ruchi/RM1	26	130	Straw	White	LS	SD	Purple
R714-3-103-1-3-2	RMI/Ruchi	31	128	Light golden	White	LS	ST	Purple ring in green plant
TN1 (susceptible check)	-	23	120	Straw	White	MS	D	Green
PTB 33 (resistant check for BPH and BLB)	-	18	185	Straw	White	LS	T	Green

^aLS = long slender, MS = medium slender. ^bSD = semidwarf, T = tall, D = dwarf.

Table 2. Reaction of rice breeding lines against brown planthopper, gall midge, and bacterial leaf blight.

Breeding line	Plant damage ^a score	Brown planthopper			Gall midge		Bacterial leaf blight	
		Rating ^b	Av feed ^c (mm ² female ⁻¹ in 24 h)	Av probing ^d marks seedling ⁻¹	(1993-95) ^e		(1993-95) ^e	
					Score	Rating	Score	Rating
R712-1-65-1-1	1.00	R	15	35	0	R	3	MR
R710-3-37-1-1-1	2.58	R	26	33	0	R	1	R
IET6286	3.20	MR	-	30	0	R	3	MR
R746-2-34-1-2-1	3.31	MR	-	20	0	R	1	R
R714-2-9-3-2-2	3.87	MR	99	22	0	R	1	R
R714-1-19-1-5-1	3.94	MR	-	24	0	R	1	R
R720-1-91-2-1-1	4.15	MR	-	17	0	R	1	R
R714-3-103-1-3-2	4.30	MR	57	25	0	R	1	R
TN1 (susceptible check)	9.00	S	160	18	9	S	9	S
PTB33 (resistant check for BPH and BLB)	1.08	R	10	42	9	S	1	R

^aBased on 4-7 replications. ^bR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, S = susceptible. ^cBased on 16-22 females. ^dAv based on 5-6 seedlings. ^eBased on 120 plants.

resistant to BLB disease and are used as donors of BLB resistance.

All seven breeding lines were found resistant to Raipur gall midge populations (Table 2). For BPH, two varieties, R712-165-1-1 and R710-3-37-1-1-1, were resistant. The BPH insect feeding on these two varieties was much reduced (15 and 26 mm² in 24 h) compared with susceptible check TN1

(160 mm² in 24 h). These breeding lines may possess an antifeedant chemical. Consequently, they also exhibited the highest probing marks (35-36 seedling⁻¹) compared with TN1 (18 seedling⁻¹). We speculate these lines may have built-in genetic resistance to BPH.

Only R710-3-37-1-1-1 is resistant to gall midge, BLB, and BPH and has all the desirable agronomic characters. It is

a semidwarf with white kernels and long, slender grains. Its hulls are light gold. It matures in 125 d, and its 1000-seed weight is 21 g.

Breeding lines R746-2-34-1-2-1, R714-2-9-3-2-2, R714-1-19-1-5-1, E720-1-91-2-1-1, and R714-3-103-1-3-2 are moderately resistant to BPH and resistant to gall midge; IET6286 is moderately resistant to BLB. ■

Pest resistance—diseases

Cross-fertility and pathogenicity of the blast fungus *Magnaporthe grisea* Sac. isolated from cultivated and wild rice in Yunnan

Li Chengyun, Yang Qinzong, Zhen Fengping, Lou Chaoxi, and Li Jingbin, Yunnan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Kunming, Yunnan 650205, China; and Kazou Ise, Japan International Research Center for Agricultural Sciences, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 305, Japan

Yunnan Province of China, a cradle of Asian cultivated rice, abounds in germplasm of both rice and rice blast fungus (*Magnaporthe grisea*). Many field races on Japanese differential rice varieties, and some field isolates from upland rice, can form the sexual stage under laboratory conditions (Li et al 1993).

Table 1. Perfect state formation of *Magnaporthe grisea* isolate from several plants in Yunnan.^a

Host plant	Cultivated rice	Wild rice	Goose grass	Finger grass	Finger millet
Cultivated rice	+	+	+	-	+
Wild rice		-	-	-	-
Goose grass			+	+	+
Finger grass				+	+
Finger millet					+

^a+ = formation; - = no formation.

Table 2. Pathogenicity of *Magnaporthe grisea* isolates from several plants in Yunnan.^a

Host plant	Cultivated rice	Wild rice	Goose grass	Finger grass	Finger millet
Cultivated rice	S	S	R	R	R
Wild rice	R	S	R	R	R
Goose grass	R	R	S	R	S
Finger grass	R	R	R	S	R
Finger millet	R	R	S	R	S

^aS = pathogenic; R = nonpathogenic.